

Data Trust: A Digital Collaboration Framework for Food Safety

Contents

A digital collaboration framework for food safety	3
Characteristics of a collaboration framework	4
Key concepts of a collaboration framework	5
Unpacking the framework	6
Implementing the framework operating model	7
Testing the framework	10
Ontology	13
Summing up Phase A	14
Next steps: Phase B	15
Appendices	16

Introduction

How should independent and competing organisations collaborate to make information accessible in a way that is safe, legally valid and demonstrably beneficial?

Our solution is a collaboration framework that supports the sharing of information and insights between participating organisations and addresses different challenges between organisations in a way that is legal and useful.

The benefits of such exchanges are clear and range from gains in efficiency and reductions in waste at a transactional level, to opportunities at sector level for supply chain optimisation and traceability. This fosters vibrant digital intelligence networks.

However, we also know that the food system as a whole is complex. Supply chains are constantly evolving, trust is continually being created, extended or eroded, and there are both technological and social inhibitors to sharing. Different approaches have been suggested, from new governance mechanisms such as the data trust concept* as an enabler of greater exploitation of artificial intelligence, to technological solutions such as distributed ledger technology or blockchain as foundations for digital supply chains.

We analysed the challenge deeply to come up with a fresh blueprint for a solution, achieved by approaching the challenge from two directions. A collection of diverse supply chain use cases provided a bottom up approach. Broader research into the overarching legal, technical and organisational challenges provided a top down vision. We brought together experts from different fields – the food industry, economists, policymakers – to take a deep dive into the use cases and balance the insights gained from fieldwork with the insights gleaned from research. The result is the digital collaboration framework for food safety.

*As recommended by Wendy Hall and Jérôme Pesenti (2017). Growing the artificial intelligence industry in the UK. Department for Digital, Culture, Media & Sport and Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy

The challenge

We need to change the way we collaborate

Existing data sharing is often limited, ad hoc and reactive

Barriers exist to limit food sector data sharing:

- Food data is often spread across multiple actors
- Lack of adoption of common standards
- Point-to-point supply chains limit collaboration

The goal

Multi-party collaboration for

- Shared expertise
- Insights into best practice
- Rapid response

The vision

A digital collaboration framework for safe sharing of information and insights in the food supply chain

- A repeatable, scalable, legally robust and compliant mechanism
- Handles data exchanges among independent organisations
- Preserves the security and independence of the organisations' data
- Enables quantifiable benefits to the participating organisations

Characteristics of a collaboration framework

	GOVERNANCE BODY	Defines standards, the trust framework for all participants in distributed network, and the basic rules of engagement between participants /machines.
	SERVICE PROVIDER	Sets up and supports shared network infrastructure, provides easy ways for approved participants to join the network.
	CORE PARTICIPANTS	People with significant roles such as governance, operations, and other designated duties.
	REGULATORS/ GOVERNMENT BODIES	Enforce legal regulations (with statutory powers where applicable) in line with the governance body guidelines.
	PARTICIPANTS	Have a say in how data usage and governance standards are implemented.

Key concepts of a collaboration framework

From the research, fieldwork and analysis we have distilled down the key concepts that need to be covered by a collaborative framework for digital collaboration. One of the key insights is that data is best retained by the partner organisations and that the solution handles the secure sharing and exchange of packets of data when and where needed. This will often need to be conducted in ways that enable insight while preventing partner organisations from having access to each other's data.

Unpacking the framework

We are now going to examine in more depth the three subsystems of the framework: interoperability, governance and membership.

Framework gateway

- The gateway to the framework offers a unified entry point for partner organisations and others, presenting all the interaction points.

Interoperability

- Interface for all interactions with the framework.
- Clear and succinct statement of purpose available to all members and non-members, readable by both humans and machines.
- A standards-compliant communication interface, based on user experience principles, enables humans and machines to make simple approaches to the data trust.
- The data API provides interoperability individually with all of the member organisations against pre-defined contractual arrangements (standards compliant and based on FAIR – findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable – principles).

Governance

- All the rules and regulations for the framework are contained within the governance layer.
- The legal structure defines the legal terms under which everything within the framework operates, including responsibilities and liabilities. It is the practical guide to what can and cannot be undertaken by the members. All of which ensures that no single partner organisation can take control.
- Rules define the responsibilities, competences and liabilities attached to the various roles to which members may be assigned.

Membership

- Directory of members and their roles and organisations may be accessible.
- Founders would enjoy special status with equal or complementary rights; associates may be added later with lesser rights and obligations; ordinary members could be created, for example as consumers of services controlled by more senior classes of membership.
- There is no limit to the number of classes of membership but details must be contained within governance layer.
- Catalogues of data and metadata may be accessible.

Reasoning engine

- Members will have access to specialist services, both human generated and machine-to-machine such as reasoning engines. A reasoning engine is an AI-enabled mechanism that handles the manipulation of the shared knowledge of the framework's members' data to deduce new information.

Implementing the framework operating model

A key feature of the governance framework is the need for a legal structure to define the operating model. There are two approaches that meet the requirements that we have defined. The choice between them will be dependent on the nature of the relationships between the participating independent organisations.

Collaboration agreement

This solution is similar to many existing digital collaboration arrangements where ad hoc solutions have emerged based on a collection of independent contractual arrangements. This could be further refined by having a modular

template available for repurposing, configurable as required. The contractual model for a collaboration agreement will be the baseline for the use cases developed for the demonstrator in phase B.

Illustrative Contractual Model

Source: Pinsent Masons

Legal entity

Given that the majority of organisations participating in our proposed framework will themselves be legal entities, or at least agencies and government departments with legal standing, it is optimal that the framework is implemented as a legal entity. This can then act as a mechanism to manage the liabilities and responsibilities of the participating organisations and the parties with which they interact. The illustrative entity model shown below indicates how some of these challenges may be addressed. Key elements include a board and representation for the data providers and other users are shown.

Ideally, the structure would be based around an existing legal entity structure such as a company limited by guarantee, for example. However,

depending on how the full scope of the framework develops, implementation may require new legislation.

The legal entity will ultimately define the key roles needed, as well as the rights and obligations of the post-holders. In addition to defining these, the framework will necessitate some clear thinking about how government organisations relate to the venture, including how they might be involved in the creation of the legal entity, or at least how they might contribute to defining the scope of the venture. Further research is needed into pre-existing examples of such structures and, in particular, ventures that have arisen from government need

Illustrative Entity Model

Source: Pinsent Masons

Testing the framework

Use case: Port health authority

A port health authority (PHA) is a junction in the food chain – it implements FSA regulatory policy, it handles food coming into the UK as a food premises and it is part of both the horizontal food supply chain and the commercial chain through the port.

The PHA we researched performs 45,000 mandatory checks each year and another 90,000+ document checks and it is part of a network of 27 other regulatory bodies in the port, from Border Force to the Environment Agency. The opportunity for more streamlined digital collaboration is clear.

We investigated the supply chain use case of chicken imported from a third country. The supply chain involves document checks (paper and digital), physical checks and complex data chains. Lessons from this use case can be used with a wide variety of commodities.

Opportunities

- Information visibility flow:** If the PHA had more information before the consignment arrived, and was able to better link-up discrete information chains, it would be able to undertake a greater proportion of compliance checks ahead of time, or make associated resources more readily available earlier, in a more strategically targeted manner. This might speed up passage through the port.

Or, if the PHA decided there was a need to sample and could let the importer know in advance, the importer could delay booking onward haulage, with less effect on supply chains. Better information sharing would enable the PHA to plan workflow more effectively – there may be 22,000 containers on board a mega ship and the PHA currently may not get information until arrival. If that information flow could be spread over two weeks prior to the ship's arrival, the PHA could deal better with peaks and troughs, which would result in operational savings.

- Linked systems:** Some PHAs have already adopted the same IT system. A collaborative data framework could link together and enable data-sharing agreements between PHAs and the FSA. That information could lead to intelligence, targeting and, from that, intelligent targeting to find non-compliant trade. Those linkages could eventually lead to uncovering serious and organised crime and deliver a more authentic, trusted and trustworthy food supply chain.

Supply chain example: chicken imports from a third country

Optimum pathway depicted – all checks ok

Testing the framework

distributed. It is a 'high-risk' product is so far as it has high value and a short shelf life, involves air / sea freight and there are ethical and food safety risks. All of these considerations make the Peruvian asparagus supply chain ripe for digital collaboration.

Opportunities

There are three key areas where there is a clear value in optimising the supply chain through more effective data sharing:

- **Duplication:** the product is checked in Peru by Senasa (the National Service of Agrarian Health) for insect and plant contamination and then again on arrival in the UK by Defra, which adds time and cost. Data could potentially provide necessary assurance assuming third party standards were recognised.
- **Waste:** around 15 shipping containers of asparagus (worth more than £1m) is wasted each year due to dehydration, rotten tips or other damage. Another £250,000 of air freighted asparagus is wasted. Although not class one standard, much of the wasted asparagus is edible and could be directed at an earlier stage in the chain to other destinations to be used in more processed products, such as soup, rather than sold fresh.
- **Traceability:** Peru has some issues with heavy metal contamination in certain fields so traceability data is crucial.

Use case: Barfoots

Barfoots is a £170m global business that grows, processes and packs premium vegetables, such as asparagus and baby sweetcorn. It operates across 7000 acres on the south coast of the UK and owns farms in Spain, Senegal and Peru. As such it is an exemplar of a large family business with extensive and complex supply chain orchestration.

It provides 85% of the UK's sweetcorn, 40% of Tenderstem and 35% of asparagus (both UK-grown and Peruvian). It processes a limited amount of prepared products, such as cut corn-on-the-cobs and squash cubes. This helps to solve some waste issues, where only part of a product is suitable for sale and consumption.

We are using the Peruvian asparagus supply chain as our use case. The crop is grown, checked and packed in Peru then sea or air freighted to the UK, where it is checked again, repacked and

Ontology

We see the successful implementation of new digital food systems as being dependent not only on robust technology platforms and economically viable business models, but also governance structures that are robust and scalable.

Such a systems approach will require clear structural elements derived from data ontologies, interoperability designs and other new ways of using data to secure trust across the food network.

"The ontology becomes the common ground to enable data exchange"

So, there is a need to develop and agree vocabularies and, subsequently, formal ontologies that define the elements that will form the basic building blocks used to describe the data-driven digital food system.

Semantic data: linked data for food safety

Source: Oxford Semantic Technologies

Summing up Phase A

The goal of this 12-month initiative by the Food Standards Agency (FSA) and the University of Lincoln is to investigate and demonstrate the viability of applying the emergent data trust concept as a solution to complex digital collaboration challenges in the food and beverage sector.

Phase A has delivered a two-pronged approach to defining a viable solution. Research into current thinking and a spectrum of relevant fields and technologies has been conducted, together with field work investigating a collection of industry-specific use cases.

The analytical research has examined existing definitions of data trusts and reflected on reports from previous projects such as the work initiated by the Office for AI and undertaken by the Open Data Institute. We set out to build a solution on three pillars: a viable business model, an integrated technology platform and a legally valid governance

framework. We therefore looked at collaborative economic models, privacy-enhancing technology solutions and various candidate legal options. We see a clear opportunity to deliver a solution that has direct benefits to participants, but also broader societal benefits, such as through the use of artificial intelligence.

A collection of use cases was identified and explored in Phase A. The analysis has provided insight into industry-specific challenges and opportunities. We have seen a picture of complex but loosely coordinated supply chains where duplication of checks, incomplete data and inefficient data flows characterise otherwise effective systems. Fortunately, despite the present demands on practitioners, we have met a favourable reception and willingness to participate in further work towards the demonstrator and the governance framework.

Demonstrator dependency diagram

Next steps: Phase B

First workstream: a technical demonstrator to act as a proof of value for the components and services being defined. This will include technical components and protocols to enable application programming interfaces (APIs) for interoperability solutions to be implemented between the datasets of independent organisations.

Second workstream: a framework that defines the governance structure. The accompanying roadmap will lay out the steps that should be taken to bring such a solution into being. The framework will describe the legal entity needed to achieve this and how independent organisations will interact with this coordinating venture.

Engagement with standards bodies such as GS1 and BSI, will be critical to producing a platform-

agnostic solution based around open standards. Semantic technologies will also be used to provide a flexible but robust interoperability solution.

The Internet of Food Things Network Plus will provide further insight into the underlying challenges, along with a series of virtual hackathons. The first workstream will also interact with the HMRC and Future Borders-funded Open Ecosystem Federation (OEF) project.

Ultimately, this initiative will produce a detailed framework that defines the elements of a legal entity for our definition of a data trust together with a clear demonstration of some possible technological implementations.

Appendices

The following appendices capture salient insights from the research and analysis conducted during the first phase of the project. The scope of this research was designed to enable us to design and develop technology-agnostic framework that addressed all of the requirements for a trustworthy information sharing solution for independent organisations.

Use case methodologies

The aim of the use cases is to gather detailed information about a small collection of diverse end-to-end (potentially seed-shelf) supply chains relevant to the UK's food system.

The goal is to capture the flows of data, the relationships between the actors in the process, the gateway decision points and trust relationships that arise from these.

Data collection workshops were held to talk through the narrative of the end-to-end use case in order to produce a document recording the objective picture with sufficient detail to inform the subsequent activities. Particular attention was applied to capturing boundary details for each of the elements: what is in, and out, of scope for the purposes of the project.

The analysis phase involves pulling the material together and producing a succinct yet thorough report together that captures the end-to-end use case. This will be achieved on a number of levels, including the issues relating to business model, governance and technology.

Topics investigated during the discussions included:

- In addition to the flow of goods, we were mostly interested in the capturing of data, and the flow of data (or not).

- Who are the main actors and agents across the journey? Who does what? What are their responsibilities? What are the hand offs? Who inspects the process? How are the inspectors validated? What are the outcomes? Who defines the outcomes?
- What are the boundary conditions for all of these elements, and how are they guaranteed? This is critical in order to gain a clear understanding of what is being defined, and what is not.
- What are the main risks? How are these key risks identified, recorded, and addressed?
- How is the safety and security of the products identified, recorded and addressed?
- Who are the main actors in the system? Who has the power and how is it manifested?
- What is the business model for the use case? Is it mainly efficiency savings and, if so, what is the size of the prize? It would be useful to have specific examples. To what extent, across the stages, does provenance contribute to the aggregation of value?
- To what extent have the processes and systems been established to address today's challenges, rather than the long-term sustainability of the elements in the supply chain? What role does data play in this balance?

- What are the reverse flows of data back up the supply chain? Does the end customer make a difference to the process?
- Looking forward, how should we address the data challenges from a governance, technical and commercial perspective?
- Are there language issues? How are they addressed?

The club addresses a particular opportunity where collective action for mutual benefit is required to overcome particular obstacles, which could not be achieved by an organisation acting on its own. These opportunities might be to improve transparency and traceability or to better manage risk, sustainability, or to improve governance and regulation. An example in the food industry is the Red Tractor organisation.

The supply chain and the incentive model

At its simplest, a supply chain is a network of organisations, people, activities, information and resources involved in moving a product or service from supplier to customer. Goods flow from raw materials to finished products with value added at each stage of the transformation and money flowing in the opposite direction. Supply chains can be simple or sophisticated with few steps or many.

The framework must deliver a viable business model on three levels:

- At the traditional level of physical products changing hands along the chain: food products made and sold, food products bought and sold, freight and haulage, packing and storage.
- At the data-enhanced level, whether provenance or prediction, the data-driven approach must create new opportunities: data collection, data analysis, targeted insurance, trade data, trends, micro marketing etc.
- At the infrastructure/service level: algorithm development and provision, reasoning engines/prediction engines, storage services, and security services will create a new tier of business opportunities

Club theory

An economic club is a joining together of parties in a supply or value chain in a membership organisation. Members can expect to share costs and benefits.

Internet of Things

The Internet of Things (IoT) refers to a family of technology solutions that capture and exploit data. These range from low cost, and often low power, devices that can capture data at multiple critical points in production and supply chains. This can include temperature and geospatial data. Actuators take data and trigger or enable other processes to happen. IoT is playing an increasing role across the manufacturing sector including food production. We are working with a couple of projects that are researching new applications in the food system.

In 2016 Professor Jeremy Frey, University of Southampton, led an investigation into the application of IoT for food safety and the results can be found here: www.itutility.ac.uk/food-safety-and-the-internet-of-things-fsio/. The IoFT Network is planning to produce an update of this investigation in the near future.

Internet of Food Things Network+

The Internet of Food Things Network+ (IoFT) is a UKRI-EPSC-funded interdisciplinary network that defragments and expands the UK's food digital economy. Through workshops, conferences, reports and funded research projects IoFT seeks to bring the whole system into the room – producers, suppliers, retailers, academics, industry, consumers – to discuss the challenges and co-create solutions.

As a primary focus, the network is investigating how artificial intelligence, data analytics and emerging technologies can enhance the

digitalisation of the UK food supply chain. It is also examining the traceability of food, and how machine learning and artificial intelligence could be used to extract value from the vast amounts of data available across the whole food supply chain, improving efficiency and reducing food waste. The overarching perspective of the network is on the societal impact of all of these transformational technologies.

With its strongly interdisciplinary approach, IoFT supports collaboration across academia, industry and policy to multiply impact. This approach allows potential solutions to be evaluated in commercial environments, and insights shared with the policymakers and regulators. The network funds projects that engage the community and have tangible outputs and it undertakes extensive horizon-scanning fieldwork.

IoFT is contributing original research the Digital Collaboration Framework for Food Safety project via working groups in three key areas: new business models, ethical dimensions and data ontologies.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)

One of the foundational elements for this work is the 2017 government-commissioned report by Dame Wendy Hall and Jérôme Pesent: Growing the artificial intelligence industry in the UK. In particular, we are building on the first recommendation of the report: 'to facilitate the sharing of data between organisations holding data and organisations looking to use data to develop AI, government and industry should deliver a programme to develop Data Trusts – proven and trusted frameworks and agreements – to ensure exchanges are secure and mutually beneficial'. The key phrase we are drawing on is 'proven and trusted frameworks and agreements', coupled with the fundamental motivation that the solution is focused on enabling the exchange of information.

Skills and competences

Delivery of the solutions encompassed within the proposed framework will require an interdisciplinary approach, both within collaborating organisations and also between them. As with other aspects of the digital economy, this will require significant upskilling across the workforce. While not all of us will have to become fully fledged data scientists, some will, and many will need greater awareness of the opportunities and risks associated with a data-driven economy. Information sharing will not deliver a risk-free food system but it should enable greater insight into the risks and opportunities. Achieving this levelling up of skills will require a degree of formalisation of roles and competences to ensure that a data steward in one organisation, for example, is aligned to those in partner organisations.

Legal models

While technical solutions and business models are important in designing the data trust framework, ultimately the governance model depends on a complex legal model that addresses and defines all of the relationships and interactions within and beyond the solution. A key challenge in achieving this is finding a balance between an ad hoc solution that starts simple but grows increasingly complex and labyrinthine, and an over-complex blueprint that risks acting as a barrier to creation. There has been a raft of preliminary work on these matters including the various projects delivered by the Open Data Institute on behalf of the Office for Artificial Intelligence. Law firm Pinsent Masons, who were involved in that work as well as this project, have reported that one clear conclusion of the earlier work was that there is not a simple one size fits all solution for a data trust. Another conclusion that we have taken as a foundation for this project is that the traditional legal understanding of a trust is not what we mean when we refer to a data trust. Rather we are attempting to define a solution that successfully encapsulates trustworthiness in information sharing in a legally compliant manner.

Standards – GS1, BSI

The BSI website describes standards as an agreed way of doing things and as coming from the distilled wisdom of people with expertise in their subject matter. There are various types of standards, including open standards, which the Cabinet Office policy paper Open standards principles categorises as enabling:

- software to interoperate through open protocols
- data exchange to occur between software and data stores

It is important to note that open standards, even when relating to information sharing, does not imply that the data itself will be openly accessible. Indeed, the application of open standards can improve security in many ways.

It is a clear goal for this project to design a framework solution that is built around standards at all levels. Ideally, this is achieved by making use of existing standards in all areas but, if necessary, through adapting or creating new standards with the ideal that these would be adopted by one or more existing standards development bodies. In particular, we see standards playing an important role in the creation of interoperability middleware – secure adaptors, in other words – to facilitate the implementation of secure interfaces between the data services of the independent organisations in a data trust, and any third party organisations that might provide services for the data trust.

Blockchain / DLT

Many of the challenges that we are looking at have been faced by blockchain deployments in the supply chain space. Supply chain data may be captured and immutably recorded in the particular kind of secure register that blockchains define. However, sooner or later, the challenge moves from the technical to the political, in the sense that a robust governance solution is needed to manage the relationships and obligations of the participants. For this reason our approach is to define a technology-agnostic approach. So blockchain, or distributed ledger technologies, may play a part in the solution, but only after other considerations have been addressed.

There may be secondary considerations to blockchain solutions, in particular the carbon footprint of any solution. Secure systems will need to be optimised to minimise resource and power usage while still addressing system requirements in terms of information sharing, trustworthy record keeping and other complex access controls.

Contact details

Steve Brewer

sbrewer@lincoln.ac.uk
University of Lincoln

Sid Kalita

Sid.kalita@food.gov.uk
Food Standards Agency

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